

De-chelation of diphenyldithiophosphate from nickel(II) complex by 1,10-phenanthroline

Sandeep Kumar^a, Mandeep Kour^a, Love Karan Rana^b, Geeta Hundal^b and Sushil K. Pandey^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 006, Jammu & Kashmir, India

E-mail : kpsushil@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar-143 005, Punjab, India

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Abstract : The reaction of $[\{3,5-(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}\}_2\text{PS}_2]_2\text{Ni}$ with 1,10-phenanthroline in chloroform in 1 : 3 molar ratio resulted in the formation of ionic complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3][\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2-3,5)_2\cdot\text{CHCl}_3]$ in which all the diphenyldithiophosphate ligands were displaced by N-donor bidentate ligand. The complex has been characterized by elemental analysis, magnetic moment, IR and single crystal X-ray analysis. The complex was crystallized in the triclinic space group $P\bar{1}$. Crystal structure reveals that the complex consists of cationic Ni^{II} ion chelated by six N atoms of the three N-donor bidentate ligands to form octahedral geometry whereas the two diphenyldithiophosphate counter-anions are non-coordinating, which are displaced from nickel(II) atom.

Keywords : Diphenyldithiophosphate, phenanthroline, single crystal X-ray.

Introduction

Square-planar complexes of 1,1-dithiolate nickel(II) react easily with monodentate nitrogen-donor ligands (in molar ratio 1 : 2) and afford octahedral nickel(II) complexes¹. Mostly the 1,1-dithiolate ligands react with metal centers to give covalently bonded complexes²⁻⁵. Ionic complexes involving 1,1-dithiolate anion which is not covalently bonded to the metal centres and are very rare⁶⁻⁹. The literature survey reveals that the reaction of transition metal complexes of 1,1-dithiolate with bidentate N-donor ligands in 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratio (metal salt : 1,1-dithiolate : N-N ligand) results in the formation of complexes comprising molar ratio of 1 : 2 : 3 (metal salt : 1,1-dithiolate : N-N ligand) as a consequence of the displacement of 1,1-dithiolate ligand by bidentate N-donor ligand⁶⁻⁹. However, the complexes with a molar ratio of 1 : 2 : 1 are also known¹⁰. Formation of ionic complexes of dialkyldithiophosphates are well reported in the literature such as $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3](\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OMe})_2)_2$ ⁷, $[\text{Mn}(\text{phen})_3](\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OEt})_2)_2$ ¹¹, $[\text{Ni}(\text{Im})_6](\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPh})_2)_2$ ¹², $[\text{Ni}(\text{Im})_6](\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_2)_2$ ¹³, $[\text{Zn}(\text{phen})_3](\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OEt})_2)_2$ ¹⁰ and $\text{Zn}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_3](\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OMe})_2)_2$ ¹⁰. In these reactions there is formation of multiple side products is also mentioned while the

reaction which we have carried resulted in the formation of only one ionic complex as major product. In this paper we report the complete de-chelation of covalent complex of nickel(II) into ionic complex by the displacement of diphenyldithiophosphate ligand from the nickel(II) complex by the N-donor bidentate ligand (1,10-phenanthroline) without the formation of any side products.

Experimental

The 3,5-dimethylphenol (Sigma-Aldrich) was used without further purification. Solvents were dried using standard methods. Moisture was carefully excluded for the synthesis of ligands throughout the experimental manipulations by using standard Schlenk's technique. The complex $[\{3,5-(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}\}_2\text{PS}_2]_2\text{Ni}$ was synthesized according to a literature procedure². Nickel was estimated gravimetrically as nickel(II)dimethylglyoximate¹⁴. Elemental analyses (C, H, N, S) were conducted using the Elemental Analyser Vario EL-III (Indian Institute of Integrative Medicine, Jammu). Infrared spectra were recorded in the range of 4000–340 cm^{-1} on a Shimadzu FT-IR spectrophotometer at the Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu.

Synthesis of [Ni(phen)₃][S₂P(OC₆H₃(CH₃)_{2-3,5})₂]₂

To a chloroform solution of [$\{(3,5\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}\}_2\text{PS}_2\}_2\text{Ni}$ (0.5 g, 0.68 mmol) was added 1,10-phenanthroline (0.36 g, 2.04 mmol) in 1 : 3 molar ratio, the purple colour of the solution changed to green immediately. After stirring for 30 min at room temperature the green solution changed into pink coloured solution. The solvent was then evaporated under vacuum, which resulted the complex as pink solid. The resulting solid was recrystallized from a chloroform/*n*-hexane mixture at room temperature. Yield : 84%; Anal. Calcd. for C₆₈H₆₀O₄P₂S₄N₆Ni : C, 64.10; H, 4.75; S, 10.07; N, 6.60; Ni, 4.61; Found : C, 61.01; H, 4.68; S, 10.02; N, 6.52; Ni, 4.54; IR (KBr) : 1587m [νC-N], 1134s [ν(P)-O-C], 848s [νP-O-(C)], 688s [νP-S]_{asym}, 578m [νP-S]_{sym}, 439w [νNi-N] cm⁻¹; μ_{eff} = 3.15 B.M.

Crystallography data collection and refinement :

The pink coloured crystals of complex [Ni(phen)₃]-[S₂P(OC₆H₃(CH₃)_{2-3,5})₂·CHCl₃] was obtained by very slow evaporation of their saturated solution in chloroform/*n*-hexane mixture (3 : 1) at room temperature. X-Ray data of complex was collected on a Bruker's Apex-II CCD diffractometer (Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar) using Mo Kα (λ = 0.71069 Å) at room temperature. The data were processed by SAINT correcting for Lorentz and polarization effects. An empirical absorption correction was applied using SADABS from Bruker. The solution was obtained by direct methods, using SIR-92¹⁵ and refined by full-matrix least squares refinement methods¹⁶ based on *F*², using SHELX-97. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. All calculations were performed using Wingx package¹⁷. Molecular drawings were obtained using DIAMOND version 2.1¹⁸. Crystallographic data, details of the data collection, structure solution and refinements are listed in Table 1.

Results and discussion

The complex was obtained as pink coloured solid and prepared by the facile reactions of bis(*O, O'*-diphenyldithiophosphato)nickel(II) complex [$\{(3,5\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}\}_2\text{PS}_2\}_2\text{Ni}$ with 1,10-phenanthroline (C₁₂H₈N₂) in 1 : 3 stoichiometric ratio in chloroform at room temperature (Scheme 1).

Table 1. Summary of the crystal structure, data collection and structure refinement parameters for complex [Ni(phen)₃][S₂P(OC₆H₃(CH₃)_{2-3,5})₂·CHCl₃]

Chemical formula	C ₃₆ H ₂₄ N ₆ Ni·2(C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₂ PS ₂)·CHCl ₃
Formula weight	1393.50
Crystal system, space group	Triclinic, <i>P</i> ⁻ 1
Temperature (K)	296
<i>a, b, c</i> (Å)	12.9340(14), 13.3880(16), 20.719(2)
α, β, γ (°)	79.561(5), 87.755(5), 70.311(5)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	3321.1(6)
<i>Z</i>	2
Radiation type	Mo Kα
Crystal size (mm)	0.12 × 0.09 × 0.07
θ range for data collection (°)	1.64–27.38
<i>T</i> _{min} , <i>T</i> _{max}	0.666, 0.746
No. of measured, independent and observed [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)] reflections	111252, 12016, 8589
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.057
(sin θ/λ) _{max} (Å ⁻¹)	0.647
<i>F</i> (000)	1444
<i>R</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 2σ(<i>F</i> ²)], <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²), <i>S</i>	0.068, 0.188, 1.03
No. of reflections	12016
No. of parameters	810
No. of restraints	0
Largest difference in peak/hole (eÅ ⁻³)	1.51/−1.45

Scheme 1. Preparation of [Ni(phen)₃][S₂P(OC₆H₃(CH₃)_{2-3,5})₂]; (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline).

IR spectrum :

The characteristic stretching bands in the IR spectrum were assigned by comparison with literature data^{1,2}. The bands at the 1134 cm^{-1} and 848 cm^{-1} may be ascribed to the $[\nu(\text{P}-\text{O}-\text{C})]$ and $[\nu\text{P}-\text{O}-(\text{C})]$ vibrations of the diphenyldithiophosphate moiety, respectively. The bands for $[\nu\text{P}-\text{S}]_{\text{asym}}$ and $[\nu\text{P}-\text{S}]_{\text{sym}}$ of the diphenyldithiophosphate moiety were observed in the region 668 cm^{-1} and 578 cm^{-1} , respectively. The band for $[\nu\text{Ni}-\text{N}]^1$ appeared at the 439 cm^{-1} . The band at the 1587 cm^{-1} has been assigned for $[\nu\text{C}-\text{N}]$ stretching vibrations of the aromatic ring of the Lewis base.

Magnetic moment measurement :

The magnetic moment analysis of the complex established octahedral geometry and the paramagnetic nature. The magnetic moment of complex is 3.15 B.M. at 298 K, which corresponds to two unpaired electrons¹.

Molecular structures of $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3][\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2-3,5)_2] \cdot 2\text{CHCl}_3$:

The complex was crystallized in the triclinic space group $P\bar{1}$. Solvent chloroform molecule is also incorporated into the crystal. The X-ray crystal structure analysis reveals that the nickel atom has an octahedral coordination geometry formed by six nitrogen of three bidentate donor moieties (1,10-phenanthroline) and two non-coordinated dithiophosphate counter-anions are lying outside the coordination sphere of nickel atom (Figs. 1 and 2). Fig. 3 illustrates packing arrangement of complex 1 along the a axis in which molecules are arranged in a zig-zag fashion. Selected bond distances and bond angles for the complex are listed in Table 2. In the complex the N-Ni bond lengths are in the range of $2.084(4)$ – $2.103(4)$ Å which are similar to the bond lengths observed in $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3](i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OCS}_2)_2$ ($2.089(2)$ – $2.107(2)$ Å)⁸ while these bond lengths are slightly shorter than that of $[\{(3,5\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}\}_2\text{PS}_2]_2\text{Ni}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2$ ($2.1310(11)$ Å)¹. The P-S bond lengths in the complex are in the range of $1.9444(18)$ – $1.9614(18)$ Å which are shorter than the P-S bond lengths in the parent square planar complex $[\{(3,5\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}\}_2\text{PS}_2]_2\text{Ni}$ ($1.9770(8)$ – $1.9778(8)$ Å)², indicating the presence of Ni-S bond and lengthening the P-S

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3][\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2-3,5)_2]$ (1) with displacement ellipsoids drawn at 50% probability level and solvent (CHCl_3) molecule is omitted for clarity.

Fig. 2. A distorted octahedral view of the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3][\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2-3,5)_2]$ (1).

bond in $[\{(3,5\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}\}_2\text{PS}_2]_2\text{Ni}^2$. The S2-P1-S1 and S4-P2-S3 bond angles in the complex are $121.41(9)^\circ$ and $120.92(9)^\circ$, respectively. These bond angles are marginally smaller than that of $[\text{Mn}(\text{phen})_3](\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OEt})_2)_2$ ($118.3(3)^\circ$ and $118.7(3)^\circ$)¹¹ but there is a prominent difference in these bond angles when compared to the parent square planar complex $[\{(3,5\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}\}_2\text{PS}_2]_2\text{Ni}$ ($104.43(4)^\circ$)². This widening of S-P1-S bond angles in the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3][\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2-3,5)_2] \cdot 2\text{CHCl}_3$ may be due to the de-chelation of S atoms of the diphenyldithiophosphate moiety from the nickel(II) atom.

Fig. 3. Unit cell packing arrangement of the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3][\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2-3,5)_2]\cdot\text{CHCl}_3$ (I) when viewed along *a* axis.

Table 2. Selected bonds length (Å) and angles (°) for complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3][\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2-3,5)_2]\cdot\text{CHCl}_3$

N1-Ni1	2.089(4)	O2-P1	1.627(3)
N2-Ni1	2.084(4)	O3-P2	1.619(3)
N3-Ni1	2.100(4)	O4-P2	1.630(3)
N4-Ni1	2.086(4)	P1-S2	1.9499(19)
N5-Ni1	2.103(4)	P1-S1	1.9572(19)
N6-Ni1	2.093(4)	P2-S4	1.9444(18)
O1-P1	1.630(4)	P2-S3	1.9614(18)
O2-P1-O1	101.61(19)	N4-Ni1-N1	91.86(15)
O2-P1-S2	112.07(15)	N2-Ni1-N6	95.90(14)
O1-P1-S2	105.59(14)	N4-Ni1-N6	169.18(15)
O2-P1-S1	103.70(14)	N1-Ni1-N6	96.82(14)
O1-P1-S1	110.80(14)	N2-Ni1-N3	96.50(14)
S2-P1-S1	121.41(9)	N4-Ni1-N3	79.37(14)
O3-P2-O4	96.88(18)	N1-Ni1-N3	170.35(14)
O3-P2-S4	112.96(14)	N6-Ni1-N3	92.36(14)
O4-P2-S4	108.92(15)	N2-Ni1-N5	171.41(15)
O3-P2-S3	103.42(14)	N4-Ni1-N5	93.45(15)
O4-P2-S3	111.05(15)	N1-Ni1-N5	93.51(15)
S4-P2-S3	120.92(9)	N6-Ni1-N5	79.62(15)
N2-Ni1-N4	91.99(15)	N3-Ni1-N5	91.04(15)
N2-Ni1-N1	79.66(14)		

Conclusions

We have reported the successful isolation of ionic complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3][\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2-3,5)_2]\cdot\text{CHCl}_3$. The complex has been characterized by elemental analysis, magnetic moment, IR and single-crystal X-ray analysis. The crystal structure analysis revealed de-chelation of two dithiophosphate moieties from the Ni^{2+} cation, which is then coordinated octahedrally by three 1,10-

phenanthroline ligands, whereas two diphenyldithiophosphates ligands are completely displaced to form non-coordinating counter-anions.

Supplementary data

CCDC 1045266 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{phen})_3][\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2-3,5)_2]\cdot\text{CHCl}_3$. The data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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